

SUCCINIC ACID IN THE TREATMENT OF SKIN DISEASES**Utayev Akbar Juraqulovich**

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Abstract: The task set before us to write this article was determination of the clinical effectiveness of the use of drugs containing hyaluronic and succinic acids for skin restoration and prevention of complications after dermatoses. To achieve our goals and objectives, we analyzed and observed 20 women aged 30 to 40 years in remission of atopic dermatitis (2 patients), seborrheic dermatitis (7), rosacea (2), acne (7), eczema (2). As a result, we came to the conclusion that the drug containing hyaluronic and succinic acids is well tolerated, helps accelerate skin regeneration, restore normal skin hydration, and normalize pigment formation. All of the above allows us to consider this procedure an effective method for correcting cosmetic skin defects after suffering from inflammatory dermatoses.

Key words: succinic acid, hyaluronic acid, treatment, skin diseases, succinic acid, atopic dermatitis, acne, eczema.

ЯКИНОВАЯ КИСЛОТА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ КОЖНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ**Утаев Акбар Журакулович**

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Аннотация: Задачей, поставленной перед нами при написании данной статьи, было определение клинической эффективности использования препаратов, содержащих гиалуроновую и янтарную кислоты, для восстановления кожи и профилактики осложнений после дерматозов. Для достижения поставленных целей и задач было проанализировано и проведено наблюдение за 20 женщинами в возрасте от 30 до 40 лет в ремиссии атопического дерматита (2 пациентки), себорейного дерматита (7), розацеа (2), акне (7), экземы (2).

В результате исследования мы пришли к выводу, что препарат, содержащий гиалуроновую и янтарную кислоты, хорошо переносится, способствует ускорению регенерации кожи, восстановлению нормальной гидратации кожи и нормализации пигментации. Всё вышеперечисленное позволяет считать данную процедуру эффективным методом коррекции косметических дефектов кожи после перенесённых воспалительных дерматозов.

Ключевые слова: Якиновая кислота, гиалуроновая кислота, лечение, кожные заболевания, атопический дерматит, акне, экзема.

INTRODUCTION

Succinic acid is extracted by processing natural amber, preserving its beneficial chemical/physical properties. It is a white crystalline powder, a natural product of living organisms. Succinic acid, which contains the active ingredient amber, is vital for the human body. It is involved in cellular energy metabolism. It is an ingredient synthesized in our own body and consists of four atoms.

Succinic acid is absolutely harmless to the human body, skin and does not cause allergies. Suitable for all skin types: dry, combination or acne-prone.

Purpose: to determine the clinical effectiveness of using drugs containing hyaluronic and succinic acids to restore skin and prevent complications after dermatoses.

Materials and methods of research: 20 women aged 30 to 40 years were observed in the remission stage of atopic dermatitis (2 patients), seborrheic dermatitis (7), rosacea (2), acne (7), eczema (2). All women received 3 procedures using a combination preparation containing succinic acid in the form of 16 mg/ml sodium succinate and 18 mg/ml hyaluronic acid. The drug was administered intradermally using the papular injection technique with a 30G needle, 2.0 ml per procedure, with an interval of 1 time every 2 weeks. Satisfaction with the results of the procedures was assessed using the International Global Aesthetic Improvement Scale (Global Aesthetic Improvement Scale ; GAIS), as well as questioning patients before and after procedures. We monitored changes in the skin at the structural level using the method of confocal laser scanning microscopy in vivo (CLSM).

Results. All patients showed positive dynamics relative to the initial indicators: a decrease in the severity of hyperpigmentation, more active skin regeneration (compared to similar areas in the same patient), improvement in skin turgor and elasticity, and an increase in the level of skin hydration. During the clinical assessment by patients and doctors of the treatment, it was revealed that the majority of them were satisfied with the result obtained (average GAIS score 2.8 points): 15 patients (75%) rated the result at 3 points, 5 patients (25%) - at 2 points. The scoring scale was also used to assess rosacea (telangiectasia), hyperpigmentation, and dry skin. The assessment was carried out on the following scale: 0 – no sign, 1 – mildly expressed, 2 – moderately expressed, 3 – strongly expressed. There was a decrease in the severity of rosacea (average score before treatment – 1.2, after treatment – 0.2), pigmentation (1.7 and 0.9 points), dry skin (1.1 and 0.1 points). In addition, the effectiveness of the therapy was assessed in each group based on a score of skin tone, heterogeneity of skin color, and moisturizing effect. The assessment was carried out on a 3-point scale, where 3 points - significantly improved, 2 points - improved, 1 point - no changes, 0 points - deterioration. A good moisturizing effect was noted in 18 (90%) patients, moderate – in 2 (10%). When examining the skin using CLSM, a decrease in the area of hyperpigmentation areas was observed, as well as a decrease in its severity, regression of hyperkeratosis, a more uniform arrangement of the fibrous structures of the dermis, and improvement in microcirculation. An increase in skin thickness due to the above processes was also noted. No allergic reactions to the administration of the drug were recorded. No effect or negative dynamics were identified during therapy.

Conclusions. The drug, containing hyaluronic and succinic acids, is well tolerated, helps accelerate skin regeneration, restore normal skin hydration, and normalize pigment formation. All of the above allows us to consider this procedure an effective method for correcting cosmetic skin defects after suffering from inflammatory dermatoses.

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